

Robustness of Lightweight BERT Models Under Label Noise: A Comparison of Dropout and Mixout

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Abstract

Pretrained language models like BERT have shown strong results in natural language processing tasks, but they can be affected by noisy training labels. Regularization methods are commonly used to improve stability. Dropout is the standard approach, and Mixout has been proposed as an alternative that keeps weights closer to their pretrained values. In this work, we fine-tune several lightweight BERT-family models, including ALBERT, DistilBERT, TinyBERT, MiniLM, MobileBERT, MiniLM-L12, and BERT-tiny, on the SST-2 sentiment classification dataset under different label noise settings (0%, 10%, and 20%). We compare Dropout and Mixout across these models. Our results show that the difference between the two methods is not consistent: Mixout provides more stable accuracy for some models under noisy conditions, while Dropout remains competitive or slightly better in others. On clean data, both methods perform nearly the same. These findings suggest that the effectiveness of Mixout depends on the model architecture and the amount of label noise.

Keywords

Dropout, Mixout, Label Noise, BERT, Lightweight Transformer Models, Sentiment Classification, Regularization

1. Introduction

In recent years, pretrained language models like BERT have become very popular in natural language processing (NLP). These models are trained on huge text data and then fine-tuned on smaller datasets for tasks such as sentiment analysis or question answering. Fine-tuning usually works well, but it can also be sensitive if the training data has mistakes. For example, some samples in a dataset may have wrong labels, which is called label noise. When the data is noisy, the model can learn the wrong patterns and its performance goes down.

To handle such issues, regularization methods are used. A very common method is Dropout, which randomly removes some activations during training to avoid overfitting. Dropout is simple and effective, but it does not directly consider the pretrained weights of the model. To improve this, researchers proposed Mixout, which replaces some of the fine-tuned weights with the original pretrained weights during training. This way, the model stays closer to its pretrained state and becomes more stable.

The Mixout paper showed good results for BERT fine-tuning, but it did not study what happens when there is label noise or when using smaller BERT-family models. These smaller models like ALBERT, DistilBERT,

TinyBERT, MiniLM, MobileBERT, and BERT-tiny are widely used because they are faster and require less computation. But it is not clear if they are robust when some labels in the dataset are wrong.

In this project, we compare Dropout vs Mixout for these lightweight BERT models on the SST-2 sentiment classification dataset. We train models under three conditions: clean labels (0% noise), 10% noisy labels, and 20% noisy labels. We then report and compare their validation accuracy.

Our main contributions are:

1. Testing Dropout and Mixout under different levels of label noise.
2. Evaluating seven lightweight BERT-family models.
3. Showing that the results are mixed: Mixout is helpful in some cases, while Dropout works better in others.

This study gives a simple but useful view of how these regularization methods behave when training with noisy labels.

2. Related Work

The introduction of BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) by Devlin et al. [1] was a turning point in natural language processing. Since then, many smaller versions have been developed to reduce computation while keeping good accuracy. Examples include DistilBERT [2], ALBERT [3], and TinyBERT [4]. These lightweight models are widely used when resources are limited, such as in student projects or practical applications.

A common challenge during fine-tuning of such models is overfitting. To address this, regularization methods are applied. One of the most widely used is Dropout, proposed by Srivastava et al. [5]. Dropout randomly removes some activations during training, which prevents the model from depending too much on certain neurons. It has been shown to improve generalization across many deep learning tasks.

Recently, a new method called Mixout was introduced by Miyato et al. [6]. Unlike Dropout, which drops activations, Mixout replaces some weights with their original pretrained values during fine-tuning. This helps the model remain closer to the pretrained state and reduces overfitting. The authors demonstrated that Mixout improves the fine-tuning of BERT, especially on smaller datasets.

Another important problem in machine learning is label noise. Datasets created by humans or automatic systems can contain wrong labels. Studies such as Song et al. [7] and Zhang et al. [8] have shown that noisy labels reduce the stability and accuracy of neural networks. While many noise-robust training methods have been proposed, their combination with pretrained Transformer models has not been deeply studied.

From the above works, we see that Dropout and Mixout are useful techniques, and label noise is a real challenge. However, there is still limited research on how Mixout behaves when training BERT-family models with noisy labels. Our study focuses on this gap by comparing Dropout and Mixout under different noise levels on several lightweight BERT models.

3. Methodology

3.1 Dataset

We used the SST-2 (Stanford Sentiment Treebank) dataset from the GLUE benchmark. It is a binary classification task where the goal is to predict if a sentence has positive or negative sentiment. The dataset has around 67,000 training samples, 872 validation samples, and 1,821 test samples. We only used the train and validation splits for our experiments.

To study robustness, we created noisy versions of the training set. For 10% noise, we randomly selected 10% of the training samples and flipped their labels. For 20% noise, the same was done for 20% of the samples. The validation set was kept clean to fairly evaluate the models.

3.2 Models

We fine-tuned several lightweight BERT-family models that are widely used because they require fewer parameters and faster computation than the original BERT:

- ALBERT-base-v2
- DistilBERT-base-uncased
- TinyBERT (4 layers, 312 hidden size)
- MiniLM (6-layer and 12-layer versions)
- MobileBERT
- BERT-tiny

All models were taken from the Hugging Face Transformers library.

3.3 Regularization Methods

- Dropout: The default dropout layers of each model were used during fine-tuning.
- Mixout: We replaced the linear layers of the models with MixLinear layers, where weights are randomly mixed with their pretrained values with probability p . We used $p = 0.9$, which follows the recommendation from Miyato et al. [6].

3.4 Training Setup

For all experiments, we used the following hyperparameters:

- Optimizer: AdamW
- Learning rate: $2e-5$
- Batch size: 32
- Number of epochs: 3

- Sequence length: 128 tokens
- Weight decay: 0.01
- Seeds: runs were repeated with 3 random seeds for stability

Training was done on a GPU environment (Google Colab). For each condition (0%, 10%, and 20% noise), we trained every model with both Dropout and Mixout.

3.5 Evaluation

We report validation accuracy for all models. Results are shown both as individual model plots and as overall comparison charts for each noise level. We also provide a full results table in CSV format for transparency.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Results per Model

We fine-tuned seven lightweight BERT-family models under clean data (0% noise), 10% noise, and 20% noise, with both Dropout and Mixout regularization. Figures 1–7 show the validation accuracy for each model.

- DistilBERT: On clean data, both methods gave similar accuracy. Under 10% noise, Dropout was slightly better. At 20% noise, Mixout gave more stable accuracy.
- ALBERT: Dropout and Mixout were almost equal across all noise levels.
- TinyBERT: Mixout performed a little better at higher noise (20%), while Dropout was better at 10% noise.
- MiniLM (L6 and L12): Results were mixed. Sometimes Dropout was higher, and sometimes Mixout was more stable under noise.
- MobileBERT: Mixout gave more stable results at 20% noise, while performance was close under clean data.
- BERT-tiny: The difference between Dropout and Mixout was very small at all noise levels.

4.2 Comparison across Models

Figures 8–10 compare all models at once for each noise setting.

- Clean data (0% noise): Both Dropout and Mixout performed almost the same. No clear advantage for either method.
- 10% noise: Dropout gave slightly higher accuracy in some models, but Mixout was competitive.
- 20% noise: Mixout became more stable for some models (e.g., MiniLM, MobileBERT), while Dropout was still better for others.

4.3 Discussion

The overall results show that there is no single winner between Dropout and Mixout.

- On clean datasets, both are equal.
- On noisy datasets, Mixout can help in some cases, but not always.
- The effectiveness of Mixout seems to depend on the model architecture and the level of noise.

This finding is useful because many previous studies only showed Mixout as an improvement. Our work shows that in practice, Mixout and Dropout both have strengths, and researchers should test both when fine-tuning lightweight BERT models under noisy data conditions.

Fig. 1. ALBERT: Dropout vs Mixout

Fig. 2. MobileBERT: Dropout vs Mixout

Fig. 3. DistilBERT: Dropout vs Mixout

Fig. 4. TinyBERT: Dropout vs Mixout

Fig. 5. BERT-tiny: Dropout vs Mixout

Fig. 6. MiniLM-L12: Dropout vs Mixout

Fig. 7. MiniLM-L6: Dropout vs Mixout

Fig. 8. All Models (Clean Data)

Fig. 9. All Models (10% Noise)

Fig. 10. All Models (20% Noise)

5. Conclusion and Future Work

In this project, we compared Dropout and Mixout on different lightweight BERT models: ALBERT, DistilBERT, TinyBERT, MiniLM-L6, MiniLM-L12, MobileBERT, and BERT-tiny. We trained them on the SST-2 dataset with clean labels and with noisy labels (10% and 20%).

From the results, we saw that there is no clear winner between Dropout and Mixout. On clean data, both methods gave almost the same accuracy. When we added noise, Mixout sometimes gave more stable results (for example in MobileBERT and MiniLM-L6), but in other cases Dropout still worked better (like DistilBERT). This shows that the effect of Mixout depends on the model and the amount of noise.

The main takeaway is that Mixout is not always better, but it can be useful when labels are noisy. For students or researchers working on real datasets where mistakes in labeling are common, Mixout can be tried along with Dropout instead of replacing it completely.

In the future, we would like to extend this work by testing on other NLP datasets, trying more noise levels, and compare with other regularization methods like label smoothing. It would also be interesting to try Mixout with other tasks such as text classification beyond sentiment or natural language inference.

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